

Experimental change actual emotional preferences by using imperceptible information impact

Cambie experimentalmente las preferencias emocionales reales mediante el uso de información no perceptible Impacto

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Received/Recibido: 06/28/2021 Accepted/Aceptado: 08/15/2021 Published/Publicado: 11/30/2021 DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5790053>

Abstract

Experience is the primary source of knowledge that provides knowledge material. Distinguish between external and internal experience. At the same time, what is experienced through the senses belongs to external experience. What is not determined by the senses, for example, desire, feeling, human reflections, are traditionally referred to as an internal experience. The article considers a fundamentally new method of research the unconscious perception. The purpose of this work is experimental verification of the ability to modify existing topical preferences using individually organized unconscious information impact. The idea of the experiment was to change the targeted level in subjects' relevant emotional appeal towards its increase to the previously unattractive object. Based on the results obtained, it can be concluded that females are more susceptible to changes in actual emotional preferences than men. Nonetheless, this trend was not statistically validated.

Keywords: internal experience, external experience, unconscious information impact, emotional appeal, emotional preferences.

Resumen

La experiencia es la principal fuente de conocimiento que proporciona material de conocimiento. Distinguir entre experiencia externa e interna. Al mismo tiempo, lo que se experimenta a través de los sentidos pertenece a la experiencia externa. Lo que no está determinado por los sentidos, por ejemplo, el deseo, el sentimiento, los reflejos humanos, se conoce tradicionalmente como una experiencia interna. El artículo considera un método de investigación fundamentalmente nuevo la percepción inconsciente. El propósito de este trabajo es la verificación experimental de la capacidad de modificar las preferencias temáticas existentes mediante el impacto de la información inconsciente organizada individualmente. La idea del experimento era cambiar el nivel objetivo en el atractivo emocional relevante de los sujetos hacia su aumento al objeto previamente poco atractivo. Con base en los resultados obtenidos, se puede concluir que las mujeres son más susceptibles a cambios en las preferencias emocionales reales que los hombres. No obstante, esta tendencia no fue validada estadísticamente.

Palabras clave: experiencia interna, experiencia externa, impacto de la información inconsciente, atractivo emocional, preferencias emocionales.

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Introduction

In this interpretation, emotional phenomena as phenomena of the psyche are, in essence, an internal experience. Thus, there is reason to believe that in this sense, most researchers use the concept of “emotional experience” and this fact explains the lack of its definition in modern Russian psychology¹⁻³.

It becomes obvious that emotional experience as a set of emotional experiences, on the one hand, is represented in the consciousness of an individual subject and is experienced by him; on the other hand, it is the property of all humanity and is transmitted and also formed in the process of mastering the language of emotions in ontogenesis^{4,5}.

Further, in the Great Soviet Encyclopedia, is defined “experience” through the category of “sensory-empirical cognition of

reality”, as the unity of knowledge, skills, and abilities.

This interpretation is correlated with how the concept of “experience” is presented in the history of philosophy, primarily in the views of representatives of the materialist⁶⁻⁹ and idealistic empiricism¹⁰⁻¹². It is known that the adherents of idealistic empiricism limited experience to the totality of sensations and perceptions, denying that it was based on objective reality and recognized subjective experience as the only reality.

Materialistic empiricism proceeded from the fact that the source of experience is the material world. In contrast to empiricism, representatives of rationalism¹³⁻¹⁵ believed that logical thinking could not be based on experience since he gives vague knowledge, leading to delusions. They believed that the mind could

comprehend the truth directly, bypassing the sensory-empirical level of knowledge¹⁶.

Dialectical materialism viewed the experience as a derivative of objective reality. Experience is a process of active, transformative influence of a person on the outside world, and at the same time, the result of this influence in the form of knowledge and skills. The concept of experience essentially coincides with the categories such as experiment and observation. On their basis, experience is formed as a result of cognition, including the totality of historically established knowledge^{4,7,17}.

Thus, in the history of philosophy, discussions around the concept of "experience" were reduced to the approval or refutation of the idea of the subjectivity of experience and the analysis of the problem of interaction between the subject and the object in the process of cognition of reality¹⁸.

In modern psychology, "experience" is not well defined, both conceptually and in empirical research. It is no coincidence that most modern dictionaries and textbooks on psychology lack a definition of this category^{11,12}.

Experience is a way of knowing reality based on its direct, sensory practical assimilation. Experience serves as an important source of information about both the objective world and the subject's mental life. In psychology, the concept of experience has acquired special features in connection with the idea that consciousness is its object like a sphere, the phenomena of which can be comprehended only as direct data of the subject's self-determination. This view, under the name of inner experience, formed the basis of introspective psychology. Going into contemplative psychology, we are not talking about the experience but inner experience^{13,14}.

In modern psychology, the appeal to the category of experience is found in the research of intelligence and thinking. So, D.N. Zavalishina⁵ operates with the category "experience" when characterizing the intelligence of an adult. In her opinion, "human experience ceases to act as a secondary component of intelligence, but rather becomes its leading component, a potential reservoir of new operational and subject knowledge, often emerging in difficult conditions of activity in the form of non-instrumental signals and intuitive mechanisms".

Some researchers consider it possible to turn to the study of the subject's experience in the context of the study of thinking. Specific structures that organize experience - mental stereotypes - set the objective orientation of thinking, i.e., determine the specific selectivity, receptivity of the subject concerning well-defined aspects of the surrounding reality, and, ultimately, determine what is usually referred to as a "mentality". However, it should be noted that in the psychology of thinking, experience is viewed as a passive, static mental formation that underlies reproductive forms of mental activity. In this sense, experience is the source of some patterns, stereotypical schemes of mental actions, used by a person in solving habitual problems¹³⁻¹⁶.

Experience is also considered a set of ideas, thought patterns inherent in everyday consciousness, which contradicts scientific knowledge. In this regard, the concept of "everyday experience" is consistently used. Thus, either the subject becomes the

bearer of several types of experience, or scientific knowledge is not a form of his experience but exists by itself, according to E. Yu. Savin⁶ should bear in mind that even every day, spontaneously formed experience still contains some generalized ways of explaining empirically observed phenomena.

The second approach to considering the concept of "experience" is associated with the study of professional experience in the concept of practical thinking. Experience is viewed as the basis of practical thinking, characterized as the unity of verbalized and non-verbalized knowledge. The main role is assigned to the metacognitive components of experience, which can act as stereotypes of professional activity.

And finally, the category of experience is considered in the concept of mental experience by M.A. Kholodnaya⁷ as the basis of intelligence. Three levels represent mental experience: cognitive experience, which includes structures that are responsible for processing information (ways of coding information, cognitive schemes, semantic structures, and conceptual mental structures); metacognitive level, which includes mental formations that allow for voluntary and involuntary regulation of one's intellectual activity; intentional experience, which includes mental structures that underlie individual intellectual tendencies (in the form of preferences, beliefs, attitudes)^{1,2}.

The experience of the subject is "both fixed forms of experience (what a person has learned in the past), and operational forms of experience (what happens in the mental experience of this person in the present), and potential forms of experience (what will appear in his mental experience as neoplasms in the near or distant future)".

Thus, the degree of concretization and the way of considering the experience of the subject in psychological concepts are different. However, it is important to note that the key place for subjective experience is given precisely as a factor that determines the intellectual behavior of the subject, but not emotional. Most often, cognitive (mental) experience is correlated with the subject's reflexive capabilities, and emotional experience is identified with internal experience, the reflexive component of which remains without due attention of researchers.

Thus, emotional experience is an integral mental education that is accessible to reflection in actual time, but its content also includes weakly reflexive or unconscious forms of organizing knowledge about emotional phenomena, a system of implicit ideas about them. The content of emotional experience can be attributed to both the past and the future.

Following the concepts of the mental experience of M.A. Kholodnaya, the subjective experience of I.S. Yakimanskaya, and referring to the results of a pilot study of psychology students' ideas about the emotional experience⁸, we summarize that the content of emotional experience includes:

1. Emotional phenomena of various modalities experienced and reflected by the subject in actual time (an operational form of the existence of emotional experience).
2. Emotional memory as the basis for constructing implicit the-

ories of emotions (a fixed form of the existence of emotional experience).

3. Implicit theories of emotions as mechanisms for processing emotional experience (a fixed form of the existence of emotional experience).
4. Attitudes and stereotypes as mechanisms of cognition of emotional experience (a fixed form of the existence of emotional experience).
5. Images and concepts (forms of reflection of emotional experience).
6. Methods of verbal and non-verbal expression of emotional experience.
7. Generalized ways of explaining (interpreting) emotional experience.
8. Interoceptive and exteroceptive types of cognition of emotional phenomena⁹.
9. Skills of managing emotions and feelings in oneself and the Other (fixed and potential forms of existence of emotional experience).

Emotional phenomena in modern psychology are mainly studied as separate manifestations of the emotional world of a person. At the same time, a person's consciousness appears to him as a subjectively experienced reality, as his emotional experience.

Materials and methods

Modern psychology is characterized by a departure from modernist paradigms, classical and non-classical rationality, freed from natural science methodology. The "objective" psychology that prevailed for almost a century and a half is being replaced by the psychology of the constructivist version, where researchers can put forward provisions of a "freer" character, taking into account the specifics of the psyche and the approach to its study¹².

Unconscious mechanisms for processing information and carrying out mental activity turn out to be much more effective because unconscious thought processes can process more information and produce its all-encompassing integration, which leads to a deep understanding of the problem and non-standard options for solving the problem. There is an unconscious thought theory that defends the primacy of the unconscious over the conscious in cognition.

The factors contributing to the productive and creative unconscious solution of the problem in the latency period are relaxation, surrounding objects and images, prompting the task, forgetting or displacement of some attitudes that interfere with the original idea¹³.

Sexuality as a phenomenon is currently being widely studied by both fundamental and industrial science. Sexuality as a phenomenon has long gone out of sight of only one science and has penetrated various spheres: culture, art, medicine, philosophy, sociology, psychology, gender. Sexuality, which is a geneti-

cally determined biological need, which is initially a sexual attraction, is the result of an integrated interaction of biological, psychological and social, cultural in the individual experience of a person, one of the most significant phenomena of human existence, and a basic human experience in the aggregate.

Sexuality, being a multidimensional problem that manifests itself on three levels of biological, social, and psychological, affects all levels of human existence. In the analysis of sexuality from the point of view of biology, the following two instinctive theories have long dominated:

According to the first theory, there is an accumulation of stimulus, according to which sexuality is fed by constantly and spontaneously accumulating internal anxiety based on an unmet physiological need that requires periodic satisfaction, like hunger or thirst. The second - the theory of stimulus reduction, assumes the satisfaction of sexual desire according to the scenario of discharge or extinction of tension and the establishment of balance in the body and is comparable to the mechanism of homeostasis. Accumulation of tension and swaying of the system, after which discharge occurs, and the system restores the usual status quo, the constancy of the environment. These two theories are in themselves reductionist and do not consider the psychological and social factors in the problem of sexuality.

Continuing the biological tradition in the concept of sexuality, the terms of sexual desire were introduced, arousal - a current, temporary psychophysiological state, is, according to R. Whalen, the function of stable excitability of a subject in a context determined by specific internal and external situations. In this case, the sexual or sexual attraction has multidimensionality and variability in its origin at the physiological level - the hormonal composition of the blood in a quantitative ratio; on the psychological level, these are emotional, behavioral, communicative conditions of manifestation in acceptable conditions and situations¹⁰.

The sexual instinct, like all human instincts, has a natural innate basis and is embedded in human life at the genetic level. A lot depends on how it is realized in a person, manifesting itself throughout life. In terms that say that the instinct is "blind", "natural", "hereditary", "impulsive" there is a reference that the emergence, maturation, and functioning of this instinct occurs apart from the will and consciousness of man. The sexual instinct is associated with such concepts as sexual desire (libido), sexual, erotic development, and so on, but how much cultural development is connected with it remains not clear enough for us to argue that this is the key to educating adolescents and young men from the point of view of educational psychology. The maturation of the instinct in the psyche, as a system within, has its characteristics that determine its nature. Being hereditary, natural sex instinct has a huge potential for energy¹¹.

Currently, components of sexuality in the literature are considered: cognitive, emotional, behavioral, spiritual. Much attention is paid to the biological determination of sexuality.

Cognitive processing is manifested in the form of a change in the perception and awareness of information related to sexuality, in a change in ideas about oneself and the world around us

in the context of sexuality, in a change in the direction of thinking. The cognitive component of sexuality includes knowledge on the topic of sexuality, gender identity, psychological gender, beliefs concerning human nature in general, beliefs about oneself and one's sexuality.

The cognitive component is closely related to emotion. The emotional sphere serves as one of the main mechanisms of internal regulation of mental activity.

The emotional sphere serves as one of the main mechanisms of internal regulation of mental activity. The emotional component of sexuality includes several emotions, including love, guilt, anxiety, etc.

The peculiarity of the bodily component consists in the bodily-sensual material basis of corporeality. The bodily component includes corporeality as "reality" (body, bodily being, sensations, physical contact) in this context.

The behavioral component is expressed in the communicative ability to build their relationships with the opposite sex, establish contacts, openly express their belonging to the same sex. The behavioral component includes sex-role behavior, contacts, and close relationships within a couple.

The existential component of sexuality is associated with the subject's understanding of himself in real situations of human existence and includes the search for the meaning of life, freedom, loneliness. The functions of sexuality are: reproductive, regulatory, health-preserving, adaptive, behavioral, recreational, relational¹⁴.

Now, the existence of the unconscious (subliminal, subsensory, subliminal) perception recognizes as undisputed. It is known to produce conditioned reflexes to unconscious stimuli that may affect the person's emotional state using unconscious stimulation. There was also the emergence of psychophysiological responses to heat-cold sensation and sexual arousal in response to specially organized by the unknown information^{1,4}.

However, debatable about the possibility of purposeful influence on complex behavioral programs caused the need- motivational and value - meaning areas of personality as conditions of such task are embedded personal importance of the information, emotional arousal, high level of activation of the psyche, the intensity and time of exposure, as well as ongoing compliance impact individual psychosomatic organization man^{1,2,4}.

The purpose of this work was experimental verification of the ability to modify existing topical preferences using individually organized unconscious information impact.

The idea of the experiment was to change the targeted level in subjects' relevant emotional appeal towards its increase to the previously unattractive object. Current emotional appeal - no appeal we define as a spontaneous ranking entity not formerly known and not having personal relationships of objects in order of preference. In this study, the spontaneous emotional appeal of objects was identical in format photographs portraits of girls and boys of Slavic appearance, taken from the Internet.

At the first stage, test-imposed ten photos of girls and portraits of young men, respectively, the test-boys - ten portraits of girls with instruction expand charges against pictures in the order appeal.

The second phase was conducted after ten days. For the second phase of unused hardware-software complex MindReader, created by the Moscow Research Institute PSYTECH under the direction of I.V. Smirnov³.

Based on the first stage results, each subject was preparing its computer procedure. The most unappealing portrait of the last-placed tenth in the first stage was built in the video images of sexually erotic nature. Throughout the procedure, which lasted 12 minutes, each subject was presented 32 pictures of sexually erotic nature, each of which is shared by the presentation of photos are rejected at the first stage of the portrait.

This video series is presented in the subject's unconscious mode by backward masking. As masking images, both for erotic photos and portraits used for special patterns that match the colors with the original pictures generates the program to realize its algorithm.

Thus, before the test, patterns on the screen flashed, and he deliberately did not accept the content of the video in disguise, although at an unconscious level sees and treated all the requirements of the image. Changing images - patterns and images of masked respectively carried by the subjects pressing a button. Should press the button during the 150 -300 msec with the appearance of each subsequent image in the case of advance or retard the program served error signals. Thereby maintaining voluntary attention and operational voltage throughout the entire procedure.

Subjects consented to participate in the experiment voluntarily and the shape of its holding, according to which they have not been reported about the true content of the experiment before it is complete. The main objective of this phase of the test for the operator acted to specifically task tracking accuracy and inerrancy timeslot switching patterns flashing on the screen.

Guide the subject read as follows:

"Your job as quickly as possible to press the button each time there is a pattern. If you are late with a push on the CRT displays remark "late" if ahead of the game - a remark "early." All these messages are duplicated in a loud voice in the headphones. The procedure ends with a voice message: "The procedure is complete."

The purpose of this procedure: to develop a positive association between the portrait and the emotions caused by the unconscious perception of sexy pictures - erotic nature.

Originally based on a preliminary acquaintance with the subjects assumed that the first sexually erotic sphere was positively significant for most participants in the experiment. Secondly, the perception of such information may cause a physiological reaction. And thirdly, unconscious perception takes action on moral-normative factors associated with education, that is shyness, and taboo that may occur when viewing sexually erotic

images in the social situation of the experiment. It could be assumed that the condition caused by unconscious visual perception of sexually erotic stimulation is emotionally positive and consequently affects the attractiveness level to the object, which was seen in this context.

Immediately after this procedure, with each test performed, pre-arranged individual repeat procedure. The subject is presented in an unconscious mode, four portraits of ten, presented at the first stage.

The first portrait was previously the most attractive; the second was the most unattractive in the first stage, used in the previous procedure, and two were neutral. The procedure is similar to the previous one, held in the unconscious mode, only used as incentives for four portraits without any additional video production. Each portrait is presented in turn ninety times. The purpose of this procedure: identify the unconscious significance of each of the four requirements objects and thereby check whether there was an unconscious attraction to change previously unattractive portrait.

Significance of objects is determined by the total time of the hierarchy of simple senso-motor reaction to each of four portraits of stimuli, from the moment of unconscious perception portrait - a stimulus to the moment you press the button, which is calculated programmatically and compared with each other by Mann-Whitney criterion. It was expected that the reaction time for significant and non-significant incentives would be significantly different. In the case of a positive attitude, the subject's reaction time for his perception will increase, and the negative will decrease.

After 10 days, held the third stage, completely similar to the first. Each subject had the same portraits at the first stage with a request to arrange them according to the degree of attraction. For comparison of two conscientious committed layouts for the presence-absence of changes in emotional preferences objects on a conscious level.

The study involved 60 students from different faculties of Petrozavodsk State University (PSU), 30 girls and 30 boys aged 19 to 23 years. For mathematical processing of results to determine the significance of differences were used Mann-Whitney test and χ^2 .

Results and discussion

Results second computer procedures female sample determined at twenty-six women, constituting 86.6% of the group, significant differences in the meantime increasing the response to one of four portraits. It is in all cases was the portrait that was built in sexually - erotic video series, i.e., most unattractive in the first stage. The results of the third stage showed that the re-conscious layout for the attractiveness of girls fourteen of twenty-six, that is 46.6% of the female sample, previously suffered most unattractive portrait from tenth place on the first three positions: eight girls put it to the first position, the second five one third.

Twelve girls, i.e., 40% of the female sample, left the most unattractive portrait at the former, the latter tenth place. Four girls, 13.4% showed no change in the emotional appeal on a conscious level, but with the second computer is not set procedure they reliable preferences of any portrait in front of others, that is their conscious preference not confirmed unconscious perception as previously attractive and not attractive portraits.

In the group of young people results from a second computer procedure, 19 people, constituting 63.4% male sample, established significant differences in the increase in the average response time to portrait, which was built in sexy - erotic video series about the three others that are the most unattractive in the first stage. The third stage results showed that the re-conscious layout on the attractiveness of the nineteen-five people, i.e., 16.6%. Male portrait sample moved from the tenth place at the beginning of the series. Three people put the unattractive portrait of the first stage in the first place, one second, one third. Fourteen of the nineteen young men, i.e., 46.6% of the male sample, left the most unattractive portrait at last, tenth place. Eleven young men, i.e., 36.6% showed no change in emotional appeal, both unconscious and on a conscious level. The second procedure is a computer and in women's group; they did not establish reliable preferences or any other front portrait.

The mathematical treatment of χ^2 by the first and third phases of the two groups established the reliability of the differences at the five percent level of significance.

Conclusion

Overall, the article's primary purpose was to investigate the experimental verification of the ability to modify existing topical preferences utilizing individually organized unconscious information impact. Given the study's finding, it can be inferred that significant differences between groups in the results of changing the initial emotional preferences as a whole were not found.

Thus, this study suggests the following conclusions:

1. There is a real opportunity to change the actual emotional preferences, using the unconscious presentation of information in a specially organized individualized single computer procedure.
2. Women are more prone to changes in actual emotional preferences than men, although this trend was not statistically validated.

Source of funding: the authors did not receive any funding.

Conflict of interest: the authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

Acknowledgments: Not applied.

References

1. Kostandov EA. Functional asymmetry of the cerebral hemispheres and unconscious perception. Moscow: Nauka. 1983.
2. Smirnov IV, Beznosyuk EV, Zhuravlev AN. Psy. Moscow: Progress Publishers. 1995.
3. Smirnov IV. Psihoèkologiã. ID "Holodilnoye delo". Moscow. 2003.
4. "The Criminal Code of the Russian Federation" of 13.06.1996 N 63-FZ (as amended on 05/04/2021, as amended on 08/04/2021) Available at http://www.consultant.ru/popular/ukrf/10_25.html
5. Zavalishina DN. Psychological analysis of operational thinking. Moscow: Nauka. 1985.
6. Savin EYu. Conceptual and metacognitive experience as the basis of intellectual competence. Moscow. 2002.
7. Kholodnaya MA. The psychology of intelligence: paradoxes of research. St. Petersburg. 2002.
8. Bergfeld AYU. Ideas about an emotional experience in beginning psychologists. Proceedings from Intern. scientific-practical conf.: Psychological cognition: actual problems. 2008.
9. Bergfeld AYU. Phenomenology of cognition of emotional phenomena. Bulletin of Perm University. Series Psychology.2009;2(28):97-117.
10. Ogarkova ES. Sexuality as a psychological phenomenon. Bulletin of Science and Education.2017;2(6(30)):112-114.
11. Adykulov AA. The phenomenon of the unconscious in the psyche and the spiritual formation of adolescents, boys and girls. Bulletin of Science and Practice. 2020;6(2):280-292.
12. Kostigrin AA. Interpretation and explanation of unconscious processes and phenomena in various spheres of human life as a constructivist position. Psychology and Psychotechnics.2020;3:17-30.
13. Laran J, Janiszewski C, Salerno A. Exploring the differences between conscious and unconscious goal pursuit. Journal of Marketing Research.2016;3(53):442-458.
14. Aizman N.I. Structural and functional analysis of sexuality. Siberian Pedagogical Journal.2009;9:275-285.
15. Abdulelah FM, Abdulbaqi MR. Fast dissolving film nanocrystal (FDNF) preparation as a new trend for solubility enhancement of poorly soluble class II drug tenoxicam. Archivos Venezolanos de Farmacología y Terapéutica. 2021;40(4):333-9. DOI:10.5281/zenodo.5218600.
16. Guerrero IM, Demera JA, Coba AG, Córdova MF, Espinosa VD, Verdugo EE, Díaz DR, Ulloa MC. Explorando el vínculo entre la enfermedad cerebrovascular y la COVID-19. Archivos Venezolanos de Farmacología y Terapéutica. 2021;40(4):361-4.
17. Andrade AV, Cruz JG, Jiménez SI, Demera JA, Ronda JR, Uzhca BS, Tinoco YJ, Lara JC. Promoción de la actividad física en los pacientes con enfermedad cardiovascular durante el confinamiento por covid-19. Síndrome Cardiometabólico. 2020;10(1):16-9. DOI:10.5281/zenodo.4527627
18. Salih SR, Haddad RA, Hassan SA. Prevalence of vulvovaginal Candidiasis and its association with Contraceptives. Archivos Venezolanos de Farmacología y Terapéutica. 2021;40(4):373-6. DOI:10.5281/zenodo.5224567